

EVIDENCE-BASED
TOXICOLOGY

EBT Evaluation Report (Acceptance Note) for TEBT-2025-0004

Submission information table

Submission Title	State of the evidence on the impacts of fishing plastic waste to coastal communities: Protocol for a Systematic Evidence Map
Submission Reference	TEBT-2025-0004
Handling Editor	Paul Whaley ORCID 0000-0003-4021-0785
Number of Reviewers	1 editor and 3 peer-reviewers
Submission Type	Method (Protocol for Planned Study) ▾
Preregistration Level	Level 1 (Open Lab Notebook Preregistration) ▾ (explanation)
Preprint DOI	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14851999
Report Number	3 ▾
Evaluation Stage	Acceptance Note ▾
Evaluation Date	26 Aug 2025
Recommendation	Accept ▾

Editor's Summary of Reviewer Comments

The authors present the planned methods for an evidence map designed to support a systems analysis approach to understanding a range of impacts and amelioration strategies relating to plastic fishing waste. During triage the editor recommended substantial revisions to further develop the planned methods, especially around the creation of the source database and how the information in the database will be presented as results for the reader. In order to secure feedback from topic specialists, and because the manuscript is functionally a complete submission, peer-reviewer comments were sought before revising the manuscript in response to the editor's comments.

Overall, the peer-reviewers were positive about the protocol. Some comments suggested a misunderstanding of the role of the protocol in planning a specific study. Many of the comments echoed the editor's comments from triage. Most of the major revisions related to ensuring the eligibility criteria were defined in a way that is fully consistent with the research goals, and a recommendation to address data collection and data storage issues at this stage of the work rather than after data has been collected. The peer-reviewers stated they were satisfied with the revisions, as was the handling editor, so the manuscript has been accepted for publication.

Final comments from peer-reviewers

1. I have carefully reviewed the authors' responses to my previous comments and the corresponding changes made to the manuscript. I am satisfied that all of my concerns have been thoroughly addressed. The clarifications provided, particularly regarding the scope of definitions, validation of the search strategy, eligibility criteria rationale, the data extraction protocol, and dashboard hosting are appropriate and well-integrated into the revised text. I have no further comments for the authors.
2. The authors revised the manuscript according to the reviewer's comments. I think this paper deserves to be published.

Acceptance Note

This manuscript has been accepted for publication by the handling editor Paul Whaley after 2 rounds of revision in response to 1 round of editorial triage and 2 rounds of peer-review.

In the editor's opinion, this protocol is a Category 1 preregistration, as the authors have previously observed or analysed at least some of the data they are collecting but they have not performed any of the analyses described in their protocol.

According to our Registered Reports policy, the manuscript following from this protocol will be accepted so long as the researchers reasonably adhere to their planned methods.

A complete record of the evaluation reports for this submission can be found at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15079256>